

College of Engineering and Technology
Department of Information Technology
ECEg3142: Object Oriented Programming
Lab No.1
Title of experiment
Lab session of Object oriented programming

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March, 2024
Mettu, Ethiopia.

Table of Contents

Abstract	i
OBJECTIVES:	i
Benefits of object oriented programming	ii
1. GUIDELINES TO STUDENTS	ii
Recommended System/Software Requirements:	ii
INTRODUCTION TO OBJECT ORIENTED PROGRAMMING	1
1.1 Types of programming paradigm.....	1
What is programming paradigm?.....	1
1.2 Overview of Object-Oriented principles	2
1.2.1 What are OOP concepts in Java?	2
Abstraction	2
Encapsulation	2
1.3 Overview of Java Programming and types of Java Program	3
1.4 Types of Java Applications/programs	3
1) Standalone Application.....	3
2) Web Application.....	4
3) Enterprise Application	4
4) Mobile Application.....	4
Features of Java.....	4
Procedure to Create and Execute Java Project in Eclipse IDE	5
Part 1 - Getting Started	10
The Java Development Kit – JDK	10
My first Java program	10
Example 1	11
Bank Account Program.....	11
Simple Program of Java	11
Requirement for Hello Java Example	11
Creating hello java example.....	12
Understanding first java program	12

Internal Details of Hello Java Program.....	13
Internal Details of Hello Java.....	13
What happens at compile time?	13
What happens at runtime?.....	13
Q) Can you save a java source file by other name than the class name?	14
Q) Can you have multiple classes in a java source file?	15
Basic in Java Programming	15
Statements and Expressions	15
Variables and Data Types	16
Declaring Variables	16
Local variables:	17
Example:	18
Example:	18
Instance variables.....	19
Example:	20
Class/static variables:.....	20
Example:	21
Notes on Variable Names	22
Strings	22
Creating Strings	22
Operator Precedence	22
Java Decision Making.....	23
The if Statement:	24
Example:	24
The if...else Statement:.....	25
Example:	25
The if...else if...else Statement:	25
Example:	26
Nested if...else Statement:.....	26
Example:	27
The switch Statement:	27
Example:	28

Java Repetition Statements	29
The while Loop:	29
Example:	30
The for Loop:	30
Example:	31
Enhanced for loop in Java:	31
Example:	32
The break Keyword:	32
Example:	33
The continue Keyword:.....	33
Example:	33
Arrays and working with arrays	34
Declaring Array Variables	34
Syntax	34
Example	34
Creating Arrays	35
Syntax	35
Example	35
Example	36
Output	37
Object and Classes	37
Objects in Java:	38
Classes in Java:	38
Constructors:	39
Creating an Object	40
Declaring a Variable to Refer to an Object.....	41
Assigning Object Reference Variables	41
Instantiating a Class	42
Initializing an Object.....	43
Accessing Instance Variables and Methods.....	46
Example:	46
OOP Concepts.....	47

Encapsulation.....	47
Advantage of Encapsulation in java.....	47
Example:	48
Inheritance.....	49
IS-A Relationship:	49
Example:	50
Types of Inheritance	51
Method Overloading	51
Example of Method Overloading by changing the no. of arguments	52
Example of Method Overloading by changing data type of argument	52
Method Overriding.....	53
Advantage of Java Method Overriding	53
Rules for Method Overriding.....	53
Example of method overriding	53
Using the super keyword:	54
What is the difference between method Overloading and Method Overriding?.....	55
Polymorphism.....	55
Static Polymorphism:.....	55
Abstraction.....	57
Abstract Class:	57
Extending Abstract Class:.....	58
Abstract Methods:.....	60
Abstract class in Java	61
Abstraction in Java.....	61
Ways to achieve Abstraction.....	61
Abstract class in Java	61
Example abstract class	61
abstract method	61
Example abstract method	61
Example of abstract class that has abstract method	62
Interfaces.....	62
Declaring Interfaces:	63

Example:	63
Interfaces have the following properties:	63
Example:	63
Implementing Interfaces:	64
Java Interface Example	65
Exception Handling	65
Exception handling overview.....	65
Exception Hierarchy	66
Exceptions Methods:.....	67
Catching Exceptions	68
Example:	68
Multiple catch Blocks:	69
The finally Keyword.....	70
Example:	71
Declaring your own Exception	72
Example:	72
Common Exceptions:.....	75
GUI and Java Applet.....	76
Overview of Applets	76
A Simple Applet Example - Hello World!.....	76
The Life Cycle of an Applet	77
Displaying Graphics in Applets	80
Playing Audio Clips.....	82
Executing an applet.....	84
Java Applets Vs Java Application.....	84
Application.....	85
Applet.....	85
Java Swing	85
Difference between AWT and Swing	85
Java Swing Examples	86
Simple Java Swing Example.....	86
Java AWT	87

Java AWT Hierarchy	87
Java AWT Example	88
AWT Example by Inheritance	88
Event Handling	89
Components of Event Handling.....	89
How Events are handled ?.....	90
Example of Event Handling.....	91
HTML code :.....	92
AWT	92
AWT Hierarchy	93
Component class	93
Creating a Frame.....	94
Creating Frame window by extending Frame class	95
Swing	97
Main Features of Swing Toolkit	97
Swing and JFC	97
JButton	97
JTextField	99
JCheckBox	101
JRadioButton.....	103
JComboBox.....	104

Abstract

The Lab Session on Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) provides a comprehensive guide to understanding and applying key concepts and principles of OOP. This lab manual is designed for students studying computer science or related fields, aiming to develop their skills in designing and implementing object-oriented programs.

The lab manual covers a range of topics, starting with an introduction to OOP and its significance in modern software development. It delves into fundamental OOP concepts, such as classes, objects, inheritance, polymorphism, and encapsulation. Each concept is explained with clear explanations and practical examples.

Throughout the lab manual, students will engage in hands-on exercises and programming tasks, using popular programming languages such as Java or C++. These exercises are carefully designed to reinforce the theoretical concepts and enhance students' understanding of OOP principles.

The lab manual also explores advanced OOP techniques, including abstract classes, interfaces, exception handling, and design patterns. Students will gain valuable insights into industry best practices and learn how to write robust, modular, and maintainable code.

In addition to the technical aspects, the lab manual emphasizes software engineering principles, such as code documentation, testing, and collaborative development using version control systems. These skills are essential for building high-quality software projects in real-world scenarios.

By the end of the lab session, students will have acquired a solid foundation in OOP and the ability to design and implement object-oriented programs effectively. The hands-on approach and practical exercises ensure that students can apply OOP concepts to real-world programming challenges.

This lab manual serves as a valuable resource for educators, providing a structured framework for OOP instruction and facilitating student learning. It equips students with the necessary skills to excel in software development and prepares them for future programming endeavors.

OBJECTIVES:

- ✓ To teach the students basics of JAVA programs and its execution.
- ✓ To teach the students the differences between C++ and Java programming.
- ✓ To make the students learn concepts like packages and interfaces.
- ✓ To make the students understand life cycle of the applets and its functionality.
- ✓ To make the students understand the usage util package.
- ✓ To teach the student, to develop java programs using interfaces.
- ✓ *Encapsulation (binding code and its data)*

Benefits of object oriented programming

- ✓ *Data security is enforced (Data Centric).*
- ✓ *Inheritance saves time (Reusability).*
- ✓ *User defined data types can be easily constructed.*
- ✓ *Large complexity in the software development can be easily managed.*

1. GUIDELINES TO STUDENTS

1. Equipment in the lab for the use of student community. Students need to maintain a proper decorum in the computer lab. Students must use the equipment with care. Any damage is caused is punishable.
2. Students are instructed to come to lab in formal dresses only.
3. Students are supposed to occupy the systems allotted to them and are not supposed to talk or Make noise in the lab.
4. Students are required to carry their observation book and lab records with completed exercises while entering the lab.
5. Lab records need to be submitted every week.
6. Students are not supposed to use pen drives in the lab.

Recommended System/Software Requirements:

- ✓ Intel based desktop PC with minimum of 2.6GHZ or faster processor with at least 25
- ✓ MB RAM and 40GB free disk space.
- ✓ Operating system: Flavor of any WINDOWS.
- ✓ Software: j2sdk1.7.
- ✓ Linux and MySQL and Eclipse or Net bean.

INTRODUCTION TO OBJECT ORIENTED PROGRAMMING

1.1 Types of programming paradigm

What is programming paradigm?

Paradigm is a model of programming based on distinct concepts that shapes the way programmers design, organize and write programs. We can also define it as a programming philosophy, approach or a model. Common programming paradigms are as follows:

- **Unstructured programming**
- **Structured (procedural) programming**
- **Modular programming and**
- **Object oriented programming**

Unstructured programming: its old programming approach where the entire program is a single algorithm. Inefficient because of code repetition as a result difficult to follow, maintain or modify.

Structured (procedural) programming: it is also known as procedure-oriented programming. Units of work are broken down to small tractable parts. Function is come to existence. Identical lines of codes segments with a specific purpose are written inseparate function. In this paradigm problem is viewed as sequence of things to be done such as getting input, calculating, displaying etc. A number of functions are written to accomplish these tasks. The primary focus of procedure-oriented is on function.

The structured programming approach to program design was based on the following advice: To solve a large problem, break the problem into several pieces and work on each piece separately; to solve each piece, treat it as a new problem which can itself be broken down into smaller problems; eventually, you will work your way down to problems that can be solved directly, without further decomposition. This approach is called top-down programming

Problems of structured or procedure-oriented programming:

- Functions have unrestricted access to global data.
- The Larger number of connections causes problems
- It makes program structure difficult to conceptualize.
- It makes program structure difficult to modify: A change made to in global data item may results in rewriting all the function that access them
- Poor modeling of real world: its arrangements of separate data and functions does a poor job of modeling things in a real world. In a real world we deal with objects (example people, car, plants... etc.) And objects have attributes (data) and behavior (function).

Modular programming: procedure or function of common use are grouped into separate modules.

Object oriented programming: It is a new programming approach that provides a way of modularizing programs by creating partitioned memory area for both data and functions that can be used as templates for creating copies of such modules on demand. This means that an object is considered to be partitioned area of computer memory that stores data and set of operations that can access the data. It incorporates the best features of procedural programming with several new powerful concepts. Object oriented programming uses **bottom up approach** of problem solving.

1.2 Overview of Object-Oriented principles

Java is a class-based object-oriented programming (OOP) language that is built around the concept of objects. OOP concepts (OOP) intend to improve code readability and reusability by defining how to structure a Java program efficiently. The main principles of object-oriented programming are:

Abstraction

- ♣ Encapsulation
- ♣ Inheritance
- ♣ Polymorphism

1.2.1 What are OOP concepts in Java?

OOP concepts allow us to create specific interactions between Java objects. They make it possible to reuse code without creating security risks or making a Java program less readable. Here are the four main principles in more detail.

Abstraction

Abstraction aims to hide complexity from the users and show them only the relevant information. For example, if you want to drive a car, you don't need to know about its internal workings. The same is true of Java classes. You can hide internal implementation details by using abstract classes or interfaces. On the abstract level, you only need to define the method signatures (name and parameter list) and let each class implement them in their own way.

Abstraction in Java:

- Hides the underlying complexity of data
- Helps to avoid repetitive code
- Presents only the signature of internal functionality
- Gives flexibility to programmers to change the implementation of the abstract behavior

Encapsulation

Encapsulation allows us to protect the data stored in a class from system-wide access. As its name suggests, it safeguards the internal contents of a class like a real-life capsule. You can implement encapsulation in Java by keeping the fields (class variables) private and providing

public getter and setter methods to each of them. Java Beans are examples of fully encapsulated classes.

1.3 Overview of Java Programming and types of Java Program

Java is a robust, general-purpose, high-level programming language and a powerful software platform. It is also object-oriented, distributed, portable and multi-threaded. Java follows the 'Write - once - run - anywhere' approach.

All Java programs must run on the Java platform that has two components, the Java Virtual Machine (JVM) and the Java Application Programming Interface (API).

There are two core types of java program namely:

1. Java applications and
2. Java applets

Where it is Used?

According to Sun, **3 billion devices run java**. There are many devices where java is currently used. Some of them are as follows:

1. Desktop Applications such as acrobat reader, media player, antivirus etc.
2. Web Applications such as irctc.co.in, javatpoint.com etc.
3. Enterprise Applications such as banking applications.
4. Mobile
5. Embedded System
6. Smart Card
7. Robotics
8. Games etc.

1.4 Types of Java Applications/programs

There are mainly 4 types of applications that can be created using java:

1) Standalone Application

It is also known as desktop application or window-based application. **An application that we need to install on every machine** such as media player, antivirus etc. AWT (Abstract Windows Toolkit) and Swing are used in java for creating standalone applications.

2) Web Application

An application that runs on the server side and creates dynamic page, is called web application. Currently, servlet, jsp, struts, jsf etc. technologies are used for creating web applications in java.

3) Enterprise Application

An application that is distributed in nature, such as banking applications etc. It has the advantage of high level security, load balancing and clustering. In java, EJB is used for creating enterprise applications.

4) Mobile Application

An application that is created for mobile devices. Currently Android and Java ME are used for creating mobile applications.

Features of Java

There is given many features of java. They are also known as **java buzzwords**. The Java Features given below are simple and easy to understand.

1. Simple
2. Object-Oriented
3. Platform independent
4. Secured
5. Robust
6. Architecture neutral
7. Portable
8. Dynamic
9. Interpreted
10. High Performance
11. Multithreaded
12. Distributed

Procedure to Create and Execute Java Project in Eclipse IDE

1. Choose File → New → Java Project from the Eclipse menu bar, as in the following Example :

2. The following window will be displayed. Enter the Project name and make sure the "Use Project folder as root for sources and class files" option is selected in the "Project layout" section as shown in the image below:

3. If you click the "Configure default..." link in the "Project Layout" area, you can make these settings your default settings for new projects. Select "Project" for the "Source and output folder" option and click "OK" button. We recommend that students configure Eclipse in this way.

4. After returning to the New Project Wizard dialog box, click Finish to actually create the Project you just described. The following screen will be displayed, denoting a workspace with one project to choose from the Package Explorer:

Note: If you forgot to close the Welcome screen (shown in the prior step), then you will not see the above window. To close the Welcome screen, click the X on the **tab Welcome** (towards the top left of the Eclipse window). Now you should see the workspace.

5. Congratulations, you have created your first Java project! But, we're only part way there. Next comes putting some substance (code) into the project to make a working program!

6. We need to create a source file where we will write our program. Rightclick on the "HelloWorld" project in the Package Explorer tabbed pane on the left side of the screen and navigate to New → Class, as in the following example:

7. Another window will be displayed. Then click in the text box labeled "Name:" and type in HelloWorld, as in the following example:

Click Finish. This step will create a new file named HelloWorld.java and add it to the project for you. It will also open a tabbed window where you can edit the HelloWorld.java source file.

8. Now that we've completed the setup we can write the program. Enter the following text into the HelloWorld.java window.

9. Go to the left Package Explorer pane. The **HelloWorld** folder should be opened, but if it is not, doubleclick on folder to open it. Then, double click on the "(default package)" to

access theHelloWorld.java file. Rightclick on the file and select Run As → Java Application.

Part 1 - Getting Started

The Java Development Kit – JDK

In order to get started in Java programming, one needs to get a recent copy of the Java JDK. This can be obtained for free by downloading it from the Sun Microsystems website,<http://java.sun.com/> Once you download and install this JDK you are ready to get started. You need a text editor as well and Microsoft's Notepad (standard with all Windows versions) suits fine.

My first Java program

Open your text editor and type the following lines of code:

```
/*  
My first program  
Version 1  
*/  
  
public class Example1 {  
public static void main (String args []) {  
System.out.println ("My first Java program");  
}  
}
```

Save the file as Example1.java

Example 2

Bank Account Program

```
int balance = 0;  
int amount;  
void deposit ()  
{  
cout<<" enter amount to deposit" <<endl;  
cin>>amount; //3000  
balance = balance + amount;  
}  
void withdrawal ()  
{  
cout<<" enter amount to withdraw" <<endl;  
cin>>amount //1000  
balance = balance - amount;  
}  
void display ()
```

```

{
cout<<" balance=" <<balance<<endl;
}
int main ()
{
deposit ();
withdraw ();
display ();
return 0;
}

```

Example 1

Bank Account Program

```

int main ()
{
int balance = 0;
int amount;
cout<<" enter amount to deposit" <<endl;
cin>>amount; //3000
balance = balance + amount;
cout<<" balance=" <<balance<<endl;
cout<<" enter amount to withdraw" <<endl;
cin>>amount //1000
balance = balance - amount;
cout<<" balance=" <<balance<<endl;
return 0;
}

```

Simple Program of Java

In this page, we will learn how to write the simple program of java. We can write a simple hello java program easily after installing the JDK.

To create a simple java program, you need to create a class that contains main method. Let's understand the requirement first.

Requirement for Hello Java Example

For executing any java program, you need to

- install the JDK if you don't have installed it, [download the JDK](#) and install it.

- set path of the jdk/bin directory. <http://www.javatpoint.com/how-to-set-path-in-java>
- create the java program
- compile and run the java program

Creating hello java example

Let's create the hello java program:

```
1. class Simple{
2.     public static void main(String args[]){
3.         System.out.println("Hello Java");
4.     }
5. }
```

Save this file as Simple.java

To compile: `javac Simple.java`

To execute: `java Simple`

Output:Hello Java

Understanding first java program

Let's see what is the meaning of class, public, static, void, main, String[], System.out.println().

- class keyword is **used to declare a class** in java.
- public keyword is **an access modifier which represents visibility**, it means it is **visible to all**.
- static is a keyword, if we declare any method as static, it is known as static method. The core advantage of static method is that **there is no need to create object to invoke the static method**. The main method is executed by the JVM, so it doesn't require to create object to invoke the main method. So it saves memory.
- void is the **return type of the method**; it means it **doesn't return any value**.
- main represents **startup of the program**.
- String[] args is used for **command line argument**.
- System.out.println() is **used print statement**.

To compile: `javac Simple.java`

To execute: `java Simple`

Internal Details of Hello Java Program

Internal Details of Hello Java

In the previous page, we have learned about the first program, how to compile and how to run the first java program. Here, we are going to learn, what happens while compiling and running the java program. Moreover, we will see some question based on the first program.

What happens at compile time?

At compile time, **java file is compiled by Java Compiler** (It does not interact with OS) and converts the java code into **bytecode**.

What happens at runtime?

At runtime, following steps are performed:

ClassLoader: is the subsystem of JVM that is used to load class files.

Bytecode Verifier: checks the code fragments for illegal code that can violate access right to objects.

Interpreter: read bytecode stream then execute the instructions.

Q) Can you save a java source file by other name than the class name?

Yes, like the figure given below illustrates:

To compile: javac Hard.java

To execute: `java Simple`

Q) Can you have multiple classes in a java source file?

Yes, like the figure given below illustrates:

The path is required to be set for using tools such as javac, java etc. If you are saving the java source file inside the jdk/bin directory, path is not required to be set because all the tools will be available in the current directory. But if you are having your java file outside the jdk/bin folder, it is necessary to set path of JDK.

Basic in Java Programming

Statements and Expressions

A statement is the simplest thing you can do in Java; a statement forms a single Java operation.

All the following are simple Java statements:

```
int i = 1;
```

```
import java.util.Scanner;
```

```
System.out.println("This motorcycle is a "+ color + " "+ make);
```

```
m.engineState = true;
```

Statements sometimes return values—for example, when you add two numbers together or test to see whether one value is equal to another. These kind of statements are called **expressions**.

The most important thing to remember about **Java statements is that each one ends with a semicolon**. Forget the semicolon and your Java program won't compile.

Java also has compound statements, or blocks, which can be placed wherever a single statement can. **Block statements are surrounded by braces ({}).**

Variables and Data Types

Variables are locations in memory in which values can be stored. *Variables are used to represent values that may be changed in the program.* They have a **name**, **type**, and **value**. Before you can use a variable, you have to declare it. After it is declared, you can then assign values to it.

Java actually has **three** kinds of variables: **instance variables**, **class variables**, and **local variables**.

Instance variables, are **used to define attributes or the state for a particular object**. Class variables are similar to instance variables, except **their values apply to all that class's instances** (and to the class itself) rather than having different values for each object.

Local variables are **declared and used inside method definitions**, for example, for index counters in loops, as temporary variables, or to hold values that you need only inside the method definition itself. They can also be used inside blocks ({}).

Once the method (or block) finishes executing, the variable definition and its value cease to exist. Use **local** variables to store information needed by a **single method** and **instance** variables to store information needed by **multiple methods** in the object.

Although all three kinds of variables are declared in much the same ways, class and instance variables are accessed and assigned in slightly different ways from local variables.

Note: Unlike other languages, Java does not have global variables—that is, variables that are global to all parts of a program. Instance and class variables can be used to communicate global information between and among objects. Remember, Java is an object-oriented language, so you should think in terms of objects and how they interact, rather than in terms of programs.

Declaring Variables

To use any variable in a Java program, you must first declare it. Variable declarations consist of **a type** and a **variable name**:

```
int myAge;
```

```
String myName;
```

```
boolean isTired;
```

Variable definitions can go **anywhere** in a method definition (that is, anywhere a regular Javastatement can go), although they are most commonly declared at the beginning of the definition before they are used:

```
public static void main (String args[]) {  
    int count;  
    String title;  
    boolean isAsleep;  
    ...  
}
```

You can string together variable names with the same type:

```
int x, y, z;  
String firstName, LastName;
```

You can also give each variable an initial value when you declare it:

```
int myAge, mySize, numShoes = 28;  
String myName = "Laura";  
boolean isTired = true;  
int a = 4, b = 5, c = 6;
```

If there are multiple variables on the same line with only one initializer (as in the first of the previous examples), the initial value applies to only the last variable in a declaration. You can also group individual variables and initializers on the same line using commas, as with the last example, above.

Local variables must be given values before they can be used (your Java program will not compile if you try to use an unassigned local variable). For this reason, it's a good idea always to give local variables initial values. Instance and class variable definitions do not have this restriction (their initial value depends on the type of the variable: null for instances of classes, 0 for numeric variables, '\0' for characters, and false for Booleans).

Local variables:

- ✓ Local variables are declared in methods, constructors, or blocks.

- ✓ Local variables are created when the method, constructor or block is entered and the variable will be destroyed once it exits the method, constructor or block.
- ✓ Access modifiers cannot be used for local variables.
- ✓ Local variables are visible only within the declared method, constructor or block.
- ✓ There is no default value for local variables so local variables should be declared and an initial value should be assigned before the first use.

Example:

Here, *age* is a local variable. This is defined inside *pupAge()* method and its scope is limited to this method only.

```
publicclassTest{
publicvoid pupAge(){
int age =0;
age= age +7;
System.out.println("Puppy age is : "+ age);
}
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
Test test =newTest();
test.pupAge();
}
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Puppy age is: 7
```

Example:

Following example uses *age* without initializing it, so it would give an error at the time of compilation.

```
publicclassTest{
publicvoid pupAge(){
int age;
age= age +7;
System.out.println("Puppy age is : "+ age);
}
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
Test test =newTest();
test.pupAge();
}
```

```
}  
}
```

This would produce the following error while compiling it:

```
Test.java:4:variable number might not have been initialized  
age = age + 7;  
      ^  
1 error
```

Instance variables

- ✓ Instance variables are declared in a class, but outside a method, constructor or any block.
- ✓ When a space is allocated for an object in the heap, a slot for each instance variable value is created.
- ✓ Instance variables are created when an object is created with the use of the keyword 'new' and destroyed when the object is destroyed.
- ✓ Instance variables hold values that must be referenced by more than one method, constructor or block, or essential parts of an object's state that must be present throughout the class.
- ✓ Instance variables can be declared in class level before or after use.
- ✓ Access modifiers can be given for instance variables.
- ✓ The instance variables are visible for all methods, constructors and block in the class. Normally, it is recommended to make these variables private (access level). However, visibility for subclasses can be given for these variables with the use of access modifiers.
- ✓ Instance variables have default values. For numbers the default value is 0, for booleans it is false and for object references it is null. Values can be assigned during the declaration or within the constructor.
- ✓ Instance variables can be accessed directly by calling the variable name inside the class. However, within static methods and different class (when instance variables are given accessibility) should be called using the fully qualified name. ***ObjectReference.VariableName***.

Example:

```
import java.io.*;

public class Employee {
    // this instance variable is visible for any child class.
    public String name;
    // salary variable is visible in Employee class only.
    private double salary;

    // The name variable is assigned in the constructor.
    public Employee(String empName) {
        name = empName;
    }
    // The salary variable is assigned a value.
    public void setSalary(double empSal) {
        salary = empSal;
    }
    // This method prints the employee details.
    public void printEmp() {
        System.out.println("name : " + name);
        System.out.println("salary : " + salary);
    }
    public static void main(String args[]) {
        Employee empOne = new Employee("Ransika");
        empOne.setSalary(1000);
        empOne.printEmp();
    }
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
name : Ransika
salary : 1000.0
```

Class/static variables:

- ✓ Class variables also known as static variables are declared with the *static* keyword in a class, but outside a method, constructor or a block.
- ✓ There would only be one copy of each class variable per class, regardless of how many objects are created from it.

- ✓ Static variables are rarely used other than being declared as constants. Constants are variables that are declared as public/private, final and static. Constant variables never change from their initial value.
- ✓ Static variables are stored in static memory. It is rare to use static variables other than declared final and used as either public or private constants.
- ✓ Static variables are created when the program starts and destroyed when the program stops.
- ✓ Visibility is similar to instance variables. However, most static variables are declared public since they must be available for users of the class.
- ✓ Default values are same as instance variables. For numbers, the default value is 0; for booleans, it is false; and for object references, it is null. Values can be assigned during the declaration or within the constructor. Additionally, values can be assigned in special static initializer blocks.
- ✓ Static variables can be accessed by calling with the class *name*. *ClassName.VariableName*.
- ✓ When declaring class variables as public static final, then variables names (constants) are all in upper case. If the static variables are not public and final the naming syntax is the same as instance and local variables.

Example:

```
import java.io.*;

public class Employee {
    // salary variable is a private static variable
    private static double salary;

    // DEPARTMENT is a constant
    public static final String DEPARTMENT = "Development ";

    public static void main(String args[]){
        salary=1000;
        System.out.println(DEPARTMENT+"average salary:"+salary);
    }
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Development average salary:1000
```

Note: If the variables are accessed from an outside class the constant should be accessed as Employee.DEPARTMENT

Notes on Variable Names

Variable names in Java can start with a letter, an underscore (`_`), or a dollar sign (`$`). They cannot start with a number. After the first character, your variable names can include any letter or number. Symbols, such as `%`, `*`, `@`, and so on, are often reserved for operators in Java, so be careful when using symbols in variable names.

Strings

Strings, which are widely used in Java programming, are a sequence of characters. In the Java programming language, strings are objects. The Java platform provides the `String` class to create and manipulate strings.

Creating Strings

The most direct way to create a string is to write:

```
String greeting = "Hello world!";
```

In this case, "Hello world!" is a *string literal*—a series of characters in your code that is enclosed in double quotes. Whenever it encounters a string literal in your code, the compiler creates a `String` object with its value—in this case, Hello world!

As with any other object, you can create `String` objects by using the `new` keyword and a constructor. The `String` class has thirteen constructors that allow you to provide the initial value of the string using different sources, such as an array of characters:

```
public class StringClass{
    public static void main(String[] args){
        char[] helloArray = { 'h', 'e', 'l', 'l', 'o', '!' };
        String helloString = new String(helloArray);
        System.out.println(helloString);
    }
}
```

The last line of this code snippet displays hello

Operator Precedence

The built-in precedence order for arithmetic operators is shown in Table 2.3. Parenthesized expressions have highest precedence and are evaluated first. Next come the multiplication, division, and modulus operators, followed by addition and subtraction. When we have an unparenthesized expression that involves both multiplication and addition, the multiplication would be done first, even if it occurs to the right of the plus sign. Operators at the same level in

the precedence hierarchy are evaluated from left to right. For example, consider the following expression:

Precedence Order	Operator	Operation
1	()	Parentheses
2	++ --	Increment, decrement
3	* / %	Multiplication, division, modulus
4	+ -	Addition, subtraction
5	<> < = > =	Relational operators
6	= = !=	Equality operators

Example:

$9 + 6 - 3 * 6 / 2$

In this case, the first operation to be applied will be the multiplication (*), followed by division (/), followed by addition (+), and then finally the subtraction (-). We can use parentheses to clarify the order of evaluation. A parenthesized expression is evaluated outward from the innermost set of parentheses:

Step 1. $((9 + 6) - ((3 * 6) / 2))$

Step 2. $((9 + 6) - (18 / 2))$

Step 3. $((9 + 6) - 9)$

Step 4. $(15 - 9)$

Step 5. 6

Parentheses can (and should) always be used to clarify the order of operations in an expression.

Java Decision Making

There are two types of decision making statements in Java. They are:

- if statements
- switch statements

The if Statement:

An if statement consists of a Boolean expression followed by one or more statements.

The syntax of an if statement is:

```
if(Boolean_expression)
{
//Statements will execute if the Boolean expression is true
}
```

If the Boolean expression evaluates to true then the block of code inside the if statement will be executed. If not the first set of code after the end of the if statement (after the closing curly brace) will be executed.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
int x =10;

if( x <20){
System.out.print("This is if statement");
}
}}

public class Ifclass {
public static void main(String[]args){
int a;int b;a=10;b=23;
if((a<b)&&(a!=b))
    {int w=9;int j=7;
int z=w+j;
System.out.println("The sum of w and j is="+ z);
System.out.println("a and b are not equal");
    } System.out.println("a and b are almost equal");
}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
This is if statement
```

The if...else Statement:

An if statement can be followed by an optional *else* statement, which executes when the Boolean expression is false.

The syntax of an if...else is:

```
if(Boolean_expression){  
//Executes when the Boolean expression is true  
}else{  
//Executes when the Boolean expression is false  
}
```

Example:

```
publicclassTest{  
  
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){  
int x =30;  
  
if( x <20){  
System.out.print("This is if statement");  
}else{  
System.out.print("This is else statement");  
}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
This is else statement
```

The if...else if...else Statement:

An if statement can be followed by an optional *else if...else* statement, which is very useful to test various conditions using single if...else if statement.

When using if , else if , else statements there are few points to keep in mind.

- An if can have zero or one else's and it must come after any else if's.
- An if can have zero to many else if's and they must come before the else.

- Once an else if succeeds, none of the remaining else if's or else's will be tested.

The syntax of an if...else is:

```
if(Boolean_expression1){
//Executes when the Boolean expression 1 is true
}elseif(Boolean_expression2){
//Executes when the Boolean expression 2 is true
}elseif(Boolean_expression3){
//Executes when the Boolean expression 3 is true
}else{
//Executes when the none of the above condition is true.
}
```

Example:

```
publicclassTest{
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
int x =30;
if( x ==10){
System.out.print("Value of X is 10");

}elseif( x ==20){
System.out.print("Value of X is 20");

}elseif( x ==30){

System.out.print("Value of X is 30");
}else{
System.out.print("This is else statement");}}} }
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Value of X is30
```

Nested if...else Statement:

It is always legal to nest if-else statements which means you can use one if or else if statement inside another if or else if statement.

The syntax for a nested if...else is as follows:

```
if(Boolean_expression1){
```

```
//Executes when the Boolean expression 1 is true
if(Boolean_expression2){
//Executes when the Boolean expression 2 is true
}
}
```

You can nest *else if...else* in the similar way as we have nested *if* statement.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
int x =30;
int y =10;

if( x ==30){
if( y ==10){
System.out.print("X = 30 and Y = 10");

}}}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
X =30and Y =10
```

The switch Statement:

A *switch* statement allows a variable to be tested for equality against a list of values. Each value is called a case, and the variable being switched on is checked for each case.

The syntax of enhanced for loop is:

```
switch(expression){
case value :
//Statements
break;//optional
case value :
//Statements
break;//optional
//You can have any number of case statements.
default://Optional
//Statements
```

```
}
```

The following rules apply to a switch statement:

- The variable used in a switch statement can only be a byte, short, int, or char.
- You can have any number of case statements within a switch. Each case is followed by the value to be compared to and a colon.
- The value for a case must be the same data type as the variable in the switch and it must be a constant or a literal.
- When the variable being switched on is equal to a case, the statements following that case will execute until a *break* statement is reached.
- When a *break* statement is reached, the switch terminates, and the flow of control jumps to the next line following the switch statement.
- Not every case needs to contain a break. If no break appears, the flow of control will *fall through* to subsequent cases until a break is reached.
- A *switch* statement can have an optional default case, which must appear at the end of the switch. The default case can be used for performing a task when none of the cases is true. No break is needed in the default case.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{  
  
    publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){  
        //char grade = args[0].charAt(0);  
        char grade ='C';  
  
        switch(grade)  
        {  
            case'A':  
                System.out.println("Excellent!");  
                break;  
            case'B':  
            case'C':  
                System.out.println("Well done");  
                break;  
            case'D':  
                System.out.println("You passed");  
            case'F':  
                System.out.println("Better try again");  
        }  
    }  
}
```

```
break;
default:
System.out.println("Invalid grade");
}
System.out.println("Your grade is "+ grade);
}}
```

Compile and run above program using various command line arguments. This would produce the following result:

```
Welldone
Your grade is a C
```

Java Repetition Statements

There may be a situation when we need to execute a block of code several number of times, and is often referred to as a loop.

Java has very flexible three looping mechanisms. You can use one of the following three loops:

- while Loop
- do...while Loop
- for Loop

As of Java 5, the *enhanced for loop* was introduced. This is mainly used for Arrays.

The while Loop:

A while loop is a control structure that allows you to repeat a task a certain number of times.

The syntax of a while loop is:

```
while(Boolean_expression)
{
//Statements
}
```

When executing, if the *boolean_expression* result is true, then the actions inside the loop will be executed. This will continue as long as the expression result is true.

Here, key point of the *while* loop is that the loop might not ever run. When the expression is tested and the result is false, the loop body will be skipped and the first statement after the while loop will be executed.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{  
  
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){  
int x =10;  
  
while( x <20){  
System.out.print("value of x : "+ x );  
x++;  
System.out.print("\n");  
}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
value of x : 10  
value of x : 11  
value of x : 12  
value of x : 13  
value of x : 14  
value of x : 15  
value of x : 16  
value of x : 17  
value of x : 18  
value of x : 19
```

The for Loop:

A for loop is a repetition control structure that allows you to efficiently write a loop that needs to execute a specific number of times.

A for loop is useful when you know how many times a task is to be repeated.

The syntax of a for loop is:

```
for(initialization;Boolean_expression; update)  
{  
//Statements  
}
```

Here is the flow of control in a for loop:

- The initialization step is executed first, and only once. This step allows you to declare and initialize any loop control variables. You are not required to put a statement here, as long as a semicolon appears.
- Next, the Boolean expression is evaluated. If it is true, the body of the loop is executed. If it is false, the body of the loop does not execute and flow of control jumps to the next statement past the for loop.
- After the body of the for loop executes, the flow of control jumps back up to the update statement. This statement allows you to update any loop control variables. This statement can be left blank, as long as a semicolon appears after the Boolean expression.
- The Boolean expression is now evaluated again. If it is true, the loop executes and the process repeats itself (body of loop, then update step, then Boolean expression). After the Boolean expression is false, the for loop terminates.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){

for(int x =10; x <20; x = x+1){
System.out.print("value of x : "+ x );
System.out.print("\n");
}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
value of x : 10
value of x : 11
value of x : 12
value of x : 13
value of x : 14
value of x : 15
value of x : 16
value of x : 17
value of x : 18
value of x : 19
```

Enhanced for loop in Java:

As of Java 5, the enhanced for loop was introduced. This is mainly used for Arrays.

The syntax of enhanced for loop is:

```
for(declaration : expression)
{
```

```
//Statements  
}
```

- **Declaration:** The newly declared block variable, which is of a type compatible with the elements of the array you are accessing. The variable will be available within the for block and its value would be the same as the current array element.
- **Expression:** This evaluates to the array you need to loop through. The expression can be an array variable or method call that returns an array.

Example:

```
publicclassTest{  
  
publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){  
int[] numbers ={ 10,20,30,40,50};  
  
for(int x : numbers ){  
System.out.print( x);  
System.out.print(",");  
}  
System.out.print("\n");  
String[] names ={"James","Larry","Tom","Lacy"};  
for(String name : names ){  
System.out.print( name );  
System.out.print(",");  
}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
10,20,30,40,50,  
James,Larry,Tom,Lacy,
```

The break Keyword:

The *break* keyword is used to stop the entire loop. The break keyword must be used inside any loop or a switch statement.

The break keyword will stop the execution of the innermost loop and start executing the next line of code after the block.

The syntax of a break is a single statement inside any loop:

```
break;
```

Example:

```
publicclassTest{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
int[] numbers ={10,20,30,40,50};

for(int x : numbers ){
if( x ==30){
    break;
}
System.out.print( x);
System.out.print("\n");
}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
10
20
```

The continue Keyword:

The *continue* keyword can be used in any of the loop control structures. It causes the loop to immediately jump to the next iteration of the loop.

- In a for loop, the continue keyword causes flow of control to immediately jump to the update statement.
- In a while loop or do/while loop, flow of control immediately jumps to the Boolean expression.

The syntax of a continue is a single statement inside any loop:

```
continue;
```

Example:

```
publicclassTest{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
int[] numbers ={10,20,30,40,50};

for(int x : numbers ){
if( x ==30){
```

```
        continue;
    }
    System.out.print( x);
    System.out.print("\n");
    }}}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
10
20
40
50
```

Arrays and working with arrays

Java provides a data structure, the **array**, which stores a fixed-size sequential collection of elements of the same type. An array is used to store a collection of data, but it is often more useful to think of an array as a collection of variables of the same type.

Instead of declaring individual variables, such as `number0`, `number1`, ..., and `number99`, you declare one array variable such as `numbers` and use `numbers[0]`, `numbers[1]`, and ..., `numbers[99]` to represent individual variables.

Declaring Array Variables

To use an array in a program, you must declare a variable to reference the array and you must specify the type of array the variable can reference. Here is the syntax for declaring an array variable.

Syntax

```
dataType[] arrayRefVar; // preferred way.
or
dataType arrayRefVar[]; // works but not preferred way.
```

Example

The following code snippets are examples of this syntax –

```
double[] myList;// preferred way.
or
double myList[];// works but not preferred way.
```

Creating Arrays

You can create an array by using the **new** operator with the following syntax.

Syntax

```
arrayRefVar = new dataType[arraySize];
```

The above statement does two things –

- It creates an array using `new dataType[arraySize]`.
- It assigns the reference of the newly created array to the variable `arrayRefVar`.

Declaring an array variable, creating an array, and assigning the reference of the array to the variable can be combined in one statement, as shown below.

```
dataType[] arrayRefVar = new dataType[arraySize];
```

Alternatively you can create arrays as follows

```
dataType[] arrayRefVar = {value0, value1, ..., valuek};
```

The array elements are accessed through the **index**. Array indices are 0-based; that is, they start from 0 to **arrayRefVar.length-1**

Example

Following statement declares an array variable, `myList`, creates an array of 10 elements of double type and assigns its reference to `myList`

```
double[] myList = new double[10];
```

Following picture represents array `myList`. Here, `myList` holds ten double values and the indices are from 0 to 9.

Example

Here is a complete example showing how to create, initialize, and process arrays

```
publicclassTestArray{  
  
    publicstaticvoid main(String[] args){  
  
        double[] myList ={ 1.9,2.9,3.4,3.5 };  
  
        // Print all the array elements  
  
        for(int i =0; i < myList.length; i++){  
  
            System.out.println(myList[i]+" ");  
  
        }  
  
        // Summing all elements  
  
        double total =0;  
  
        for(int i =0; i < myList.length; i++){  
  
            total+= myList[i];  
  
        }  
  
        System.out.println("Total is "+ total);  
  
        // Finding the largest element  
  
        double max = myList[0];  
  
        for(int i =1; i < myList.length; i++){  
  
            if(myList[i]> max) max = myList[i];  
  
        }  
  
        System.out.println("Max is "+ max);  
  
    }  
}
```

This will produce the following result –

Output

```
1.9
2.9
3.4
3.5
Total is 11.7
Max is 3.5
```

Object and Classes

Java is an Object-Oriented Language. As a language that has the Object Oriented feature, Java supports the following fundamental concepts:

- Polymorphism
- Inheritance
- Encapsulation
- Abstraction
- Classes
- Objects
- Instance
- Method
- Message Parsing

- **Object** - Objects have states and behaviors. Example: A dog has states - color, name, breed as well as behaviors -wagging, barking, and eating. An object is an instance of a class.
- **Class** - A class can be defined as a template/blue print that describes the behaviors and states that object of its type support.

Objects in Java:

Let us now look deep into what are objects. If we consider the real-world we can find many objects around us like Cars, Dogs, Humans, etc. All these objects have a state and behavior.

If we consider a dog, then its state is - name, breed, color, and the behavior is - barking, wagging, running

If you compare the software object with a real world object, they have very similar characteristics.

Software objects also have a state and behavior. A software object's state is stored in fields and behavior is shown via methods.

So, in software development, methods operate on the internal state of an object and the object-to-object communication is done via methods.

Classes in Java:

A class is a blue print from which individual objects are created.

A sample of a class is given below:

```
public class Dog {  
    String breed;  
    int age;  
    String color;  
  
    void barking(){  
    }  
  
    void hungry(){  
    }  
  
    void sleeping(){  
    }  
}
```

A class can contain any of the following variable types.

- **Local variables:** Variables defined **inside** methods, constructors or blocks are called local variables. The variable will be *declared* and *initialized* within the method and the variable will be *destroyed* when the method has completed.
- **Instance variables:** Instance variables are variables **within a class but outside** any method. These variables are **instantiated** when the class is loaded. Instance variables can be accessed from inside any method, constructor or blocks of that particular class.
- **Class variables:** Class variables are variables declared with in a class, outside any method, with the **static** keyword.

A class can have **any** number of methods to access the value of various kinds of methods. In the above example, barking(), hungry() and sleeping() are methods.

Constructors:

When discussing about classes, one of the most important sub topic would be constructors. **Every** class has a constructor. If we do not **explicitly write** a constructor for a class, the Java compiler builds a **default** constructor for that class.

Each time a **new** object is **created**, at least one constructor will be invoked. The main rule of constructors is that they **should have the same name as the class**. A class can have **more than one** constructor.

Here are the key differences between a constructor and a method:

- A constructor doesn't have a return type.
- The name of the constructor must be the same as the name of the class.
- Unlike methods, constructors are not considered members of a class.
- A constructor is called automatically when a new instance of an object is created.

Here's the basic format for coding a constructor:

```
public ClassName (parameter-list)
{
statements...
}
```

Constructors have one purpose in life: to create an instance of a class. This can also be called creating an object.

The purpose of methods, by contrast, is much more general. A method's basic function is to execute Java code.

Example of a constructor is given below:

```
publicclassPuppy{
publicPuppy(){
}
publicPuppy(String name){
// This constructor has one parameter, name.
}
}
```

Java also supports **Singleton Classes** where you would be able to create only one instance of a class.

Creating an Object

As mentioned previously, a class provides the blueprints for objects. So, basically an object is created from a class. In Java, the **new** key word is used to create new objects.

There are three steps when creating an object from a class:

- **Declaration:** A variable declaration with a variable name with an object type.
- **Instantiation:** The 'new' key word is used to create the object.
- **Initialization:** The 'new' keyword is followed by a call to a constructor. This call initializes the new object.

Example of creating an object is given below:

```
publicclassPuppy{

publicPuppy(String name){
// This constructor has one parameter, name.
System.out.println("Passed Name is :"+ name );
}
publicstaticvoid main(String[]args){
// Following statement would create an object myPuppy
Puppy myPuppy =newPuppy(" Tolosa");
}
}
```

If we compile and run the above program, then it would produce the following result:

```
PassedNameis:Tolosa
```

Declaring a Variable to Refer to an Object

Previously, you learned that to declare a variable, you write:

Type name;

This notifies the compiler that you will use *name* to refer to data whose type is *type*. With a primitive variable, this declaration also reserves the proper amount of memory for the variable.

You can also declare a reference variable on its own line. For example:

Point originOne;

If you declare `originOne` like this, its value will be undetermined until an object is actually created and assigned to it. Simply declaring a reference variable does not create an object. For that, you need to use the `new` operator, as described in the next section. You must assign an object to `originOne` before you use it in your code. Otherwise, you will get a compiler error.

A variable in this state, which currently references no object, can be illustrated as follows (the variable name, `originOne`, plus a reference pointing to nothing):

Assigning Object Reference Variables

Object reference variables act differently than you might expect when an assignment takes place. For example, what do you think the following fragment does?

```
Box b1 = new Box ();  
Box b2 = b1;
```

You might think that `b2` is being assigned a reference to a copy of the object referred to by `b1`. That is, you might think that `b1` and `b2` refer to separate and distinct objects. However, this would be wrong. Instead, after this fragment executes, `b1` and `b2` will both refer to the *same* object. The assignment of `b1` to `b2` did not allocate any memory or copy any part of the original object. It simply makes `b2` refer to the same object as does `b1`. Thus, any changes made to the object through `b2` will affect the object to which `b1` is referring, since they are the same object.

This situation is depicted here:

Although **b1** and **b2** both refer to the same object, they are not linked in any other way. For example, a subsequent assignment to **b1** will simply **unhook b1** from the original object without affecting the object or affecting **b2**. For example:

```
Box b1 = new Box();
Box b2 = b1;
// ...
b1 = null;
```

Here, **b1** has been set to **null**, but **b2** still points to the original object.

REMEMBER: When you assign one object reference variable to another object reference variable, you aren't creating a copy of the object, you are only making a copy of the reference.

Instantiating a Class

The `new` operator instantiates a class by allocating memory for a new object and returning a reference to that memory. The `new` operator also invokes the object constructor.

Note: The phrase "instantiating a class" means the same thing as "creating an object." When you create an object, you are creating an "instance" of a class, therefore "instantiating" a class.

The `new` operator requires a single, postfix argument: a call to a constructor. The name of the constructor provides the name of the class to instantiate.

The `new` operator returns a reference to the object it created. This reference is usually assigned to a variable of the appropriate type, like:

```
Point originOne = new Point(23, 94);
```

The reference returned by the `new` operator does not have to be assigned to a variable. It can also be used directly in an expression.

For example:

```
int height = new Rectangle().height;
```

This statement will be discussed in the next section.

Initializing an Object

Here's the code for the Point class:

```
public class Point {  
    public int x = 0;  
    public int y = 0;  
    //constructor  
    public Point(int a, int b) {  
        x = a;  
        y = b;  
    }  
}
```

This class contains a single constructor. You can recognize a constructor because its declaration uses the same name as the class and it has no return type. The constructor in the Point class takes two integer arguments, as declared by the code (int a, int b). The following statement provides 23 and 94 as values for those arguments:

```
Point originOne = new Point(23, 94);
```

The result of executing this statement can be illustrated in the next figure:

Here's the code for the Rectangle class, which contains four constructors:

```
Public class Rectangle {
Public int width = 0;
Public int height = 0;
public Point origin;

    // four constructors
public Rectangle() {
origin = new Point(0, 0);
    }
public Rectangle(Point p) {
origin = p;
    }
public Rectangle(int w, int h) {
origin = new Point(0, 0);
width = w;
height = h;
    }
public Rectangle(Point p, int w, int h) {
origin = p;
width = w;
height = h;
    }

    // a method for moving the rectangle
public void move(int x, int y) {
    origin.x = x;
    origin.y = y;
    }
    // a method for computing the area of the rectangle
public int getArea() {
return width * height;
    }
}
```

Each constructor lets you provide initial values for the rectangle's origin, width, and height, using both primitive and reference types. If a class has multiple constructors, they must have different signatures. The Java compiler differentiates the constructors based on the number and the type of the arguments. When the Java compiler encounters the following code, it knows to call the

constructor in the Rectangle class that requires a Point argument followed by two integer arguments:

```
Rectangle rectOne = new Rectangle(originOne, 100, 200);
```

This calls one of Rectangle's constructors that initializes origin to originOne. Also, the constructor sets width to 100 and height to 200. Now there are two references to the samePoint object—an object can have multiple references to it, as shown in the next figure:

The following line of code calls the Rectangle constructor that requires two integer arguments, which provide the initial values for width and height. If you inspect the code within the constructor, you will see that it creates a new Point object whose x and y values are initialized to 0:

```
Rectangle rectTwo = new Rectangle(50, 100);
```

The Rectangle constructor used in the following statement doesn't take any arguments, so it's called a *no-argument constructor*:

```
Rectangle rect = new Rectangle();
```

All classes have at least one constructor. If a class does not explicitly declare any, the Java compiler automatically provides a no-argument constructor, called the *default constructor*. This default constructor calls the class parent's no-argument constructor, or the Object constructor if the class has no other parent. If the parent has no constructor (Object does have one), the compiler will reject the program.

Accessing Instance Variables and Methods

Instance variables and methods are accessed via created objects. To access an instance variable, the fully qualified path should be as follows:

```
/* First create an object */
ObjectReference=newConstructor();

/* Now call a variable as follows */
ObjectReference.variableName;

/* Now you can call a class method as follows */
ObjectReference.MethodName();
```

Example:

This example explains how to access instance variables and methods of a class:

```
publicclassPuppy{

int puppyAge;

publicPuppy(String name){
// This constructor has one parameter, name.
System.out.println("Passed Name is :"+ name );
}
publicvoid setAge(int age ){
puppyAge= age;
}

publicint getAge(){
System.out.println("Puppy's age is :"+ puppyAge );
return puppyAge;
}
publicstaticvoid main(String[]args){
/* Object creation */
Puppy myPuppy =newPuppy("tommy");

/* Call class method to set puppy's age */
myPuppy.setAge(2);

/* Call another class method to get puppy's age */
```

```
myPuppy.getAge();

/* You can access instance variable as follows as well */
System.out.println("Variable Value :"+ myPuppy.puppyAge );
}
}
```

If we compile and run the above program, then it would produce the following result:

```
PassedNameis:tommy
Puppy's age is :2
Variable Value :2
```

OOP Concepts

Encapsulation

Encapsulation is one of the four fundamental OOP concepts. The other three are inheritance, polymorphism, and abstraction.

Encapsulation in java is a *process of wrapping code and data together into a single unit*, for example capsule i.e. mixed of several medicines.

It is the **technique of making the fields in a class private and providing access to the fields via public methods**. If a field is declared private, it cannot be accessed by anyone outside the class, thereby hiding the fields within the class. For this reason, encapsulation is also referred to as **data hiding**.

Encapsulation can be described as a **protective barrier that prevents the code and data being randomly accessed by other code defined outside the class**. Access to the data and code is tightly controlled by an interface.

Advantage of Encapsulation in java

- The fields of a class can be made read-only or write-only.
- A class can have total control over what is stored in its fields.
- The users of a class do not know how the class stores its data. A class can change the data type of a field and users of the class do not need to change any of their code.

Example:

Let us look at an example that depicts encapsulation:

```
/* File name : EncapTest.java */
PublicclassEncapTest{

privateString name;
privateString idNum;
privateint age;

publicint getAge(){
return age;
}
publicString getName(){
return name;
}
publicString getIdNum(){
return idNum;
}
publicvoid setAge(int newAge){
age= newAge;
}
publicvoid setName(String newName){
name= newName;
}
publicvoid setIdNum(String newId){
idNum= newId;
}
}
```

The public methods are the access points to this class' fields from the outside java world. Normally, these methods are referred as getters and setters. Therefore, any class that wants to access the variables should access them through these getters and setters.

The variables of the EncapTest class can be accessed as below:

```
/* File name : RunEncap.java */
publicclassRunEncap{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){
EncapTest encap =newEncapTest();
encap.setName("James");
encap.setAge(20);
encap.setIdNum("12343ms");
}
```

```
System.out.print("Name : "+ encap.getName()+" Age : "+ encap.getAge());
}
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Name:JamesAge:20
```

Inheritance

Inheritance can be defined as the process where one object acquires the properties of another. With the use of inheritance the information is made manageable in a hierarchical order.

When we talk about inheritance, the most commonly used keyword would be **extends** and **implements**. These words would determine whether one object IS-A type of another. By using these keywords we can make one object acquire the properties of another object.

IS-A Relationship:

IS-A is a way of saying: This object is a type of that object. Let us see how the **extends** keyword is used to achieve inheritance.

```
publicclassAnimal{
}
publicclassMammalextendsAnimal{
}
publicclassReptileextendsAnimal{
}
publicclassDogextendsMammal{
}
```

Now, based on the above example, In Object Oriented terms, the following are true:

- Animal is the super class of Mammal class.
- Animal is the super class of Reptile class.
- Mammal and Reptile are subclasses of Animal class.
- Dog is the subclass of both Mammal and Animal classes.

Now, if we consider the IS-A relationship, we can say:

- Mammal IS-A Animal

- Reptile IS-A Animal
- Dog IS-A Mammal
- Hence: Dog IS-A Animal as well Mammal

With use of the **extends** keyword the subclasses will be able to inherit all the properties of the super class except for the private properties of the super class.

We can assure that Mammal is actually an Animal with the use of the instance operator.

Example:

```
public class Dog extends Mammal {

public static void main(String args[]){

Animal a = new Animal();

Mammal m = new Mammal();

Dog d = new Dog();

System.out.println(a instanceof Animal);

System.out.println(d instanceof Mammal);

System.out.println(d instanceof Dog);

}}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
true
true
true
```

```
class Employee{
float salary=40000;
}
class Programmer extends Employee{
int bonus=10000;
public static void main(String args[]){
```

```
Programmer p=new Programmer();
System.out.println("Programmer salary is:"+p.salary);
System.out.println("Bonus of Programmer is:"+p.bonus);
}
}
```

Output

Programmer salary is:40000.0

Bonus of programmer is:10000

In the above example, Programmer object can access the field of own class as well as of Employee class i.e. code reusability.

Types of Inheritance

On the basis of class, there can be three types of inheritance: single, multilevel and hierarchical in java.

In java programming, multiple and hybrid inheritance is supported through interface only.

Method Overloading

If a class has multiple methods by same name but different parameters, it is known as **Method Overloading**. If we have to perform only one operation, having same name of the methods increases the readability of the program. Suppose you have to perform addition of the given numbers but there can be any number of arguments, if you write the method such as a(int,int) for two parameters, and b(int,int,int) for three parameters then it may be difficult for you as well as other programmers to understand the behavior of the method because its name differs. So, we perform method overloading to figure out the program quickly.

There are two ways to overload the method in java

1. By changing number of arguments
2. By changing the data type

In java, Method Overloading is not possible by changing the return type of the method.

Example of Method Overloading by changing the no. of arguments

In this example, we have created two overloaded methods, first sum method performs addition of two numbers and second sum method performs addition of three numbers.

```
1. class Calculation{
2.   void sum(int a,int b){System.out.println(a+b);}
3.   void sum(int a,int b,int c){System.out.println(a+b+c);}
4.
5.   public static void main(String args[]){
6.     Calculation obj=new Calculation();
7.     obj.sum(10,10,10);
8.     obj.sum(20,20);
9.
10.  }
11. }
```

Output:30

40

Example of Method Overloading by changing data type of argument

In this example, we have created two overloaded methods that differ in data type. The first sum method receives two integer arguments and second sum method receives two double arguments.

```
1. class Calculation2{
2.   void sum(int a,int b){System.out.println(a+b);}
3.   void sum(double a,double b){System.out.println(a+b);}
4.
5.   public static void main(String args[]){
6.     Calculation2 obj=new Calculation2();
7.     obj.sum(10.5,10.5);
8.     obj.sum(20,20);
9.
10.  }
11. }
```

Output:21.0

40

Method Overriding

If subclass (child class) has the same method as declared in the parent class, it is known as **method overriding**.

In other words, if subclass provides the specific implementation of the method that has been provided by one of its parent class, it is known as Method Overriding.

Advantage of Java Method Overriding

- Method Overriding is used to provide specific implementation of a method that is already provided by its super class.
- Method Overriding is used for Runtime Polymorphism

Rules for Method Overriding

- Method must have same name as in the parent class
- Method must have same parameter as in the parent class.
- Instance methods can be overridden only if they are inherited by the subclass.
- A method declared final cannot be overridden.
- A method declared static cannot be overridden but can be re-declared.
- If a method cannot be inherited, then it cannot be overridden.
- A subclass within the same package as the instance's superclass can override any superclass method that is not declared private or final.
- A subclass in a different package can only override the non-final methods declared public or protected.
- An overriding method can throw any unchecked exceptions, regardless of whether the overridden method throws exceptions or not. However, the overriding method should not throw checked exceptions that are new or broader than the ones declared by the overridden method. The overriding method can throw narrower or fewer exceptions than the overridden method.
- Constructors cannot be overridden.

Example of method overriding

In this example, we have defined the run method in the subclass as defined in the parent class but it has some specific implementation. The name and parameter of the method is same and there is IS-A relationship between the classes, so there is method overriding.

1. **class** Vehicle{
2. **void** run(){System.out.println("Vehicle is running");}
3. **class** Bike2 **extends** Vehicle{
4. **void** run(){System.out.println("Bike is running safely");}
- 5.
6. **public static void** main(String args[]){
7. Bike2 obj = **new** Bike2();
8. obj.run();
9. }
10. }

Output:Bike is running safely

Using the super keyword:

When invoking a superclass version of an overridden method the **super** keyword is used.

```

ClassAnimal{

publicvoid move(){
System.out.println("Animals can move");
}
}
classDogextendAnimal{

publicvoid move(){
super.move();// invokes the super class method
System.out.println("Dogs can walk and run");
}
}
publicclassTestDog{

publicstaticvoid main(String args[]){

Animal b =newDog();// Animal reference but Dog object
b.move();//Runs the method in Dog class

}
}

```

This would produce the following result:

```

Animals can move
Dogs can walk and run

```

What is the difference between method Overloading and Method Overriding?

There are three basic differences between the method overloading and method overriding. They are as follows:

Method Overloading

- 1) Method overloading is used to increase the readability of the program.
- 2) Method overloading is performed within a class.
- 3) In case of method overloading parameter must be different.

Method Overriding

- Method overriding is used to provide the specific implementation of the method that is already provided by its super class.
- Method overriding occurs in two classes that have IS-A relationship.
- In case of method overriding parameter must be same.

Polymorphism

The word ‘polymorphism’ literally means ‘a state of having many shapes’ or ‘the capacity to take on different forms’. When applied to object oriented programming languages like Java, it describes a language’s ability to process objects of various types and classes through a single, uniform interface.

Polymorphism in Java has two types: Compile time polymorphism (static binding) and Runtime polymorphism (dynamic binding). Method overloading is an example of static polymorphism, while method overriding is an example of dynamic polymorphism.

An important example of polymorphism is how a parent class refers to a child class object. In fact, any object that satisfies more than one IS-A relationship is polymorphic in nature.

For instance, let’s consider a class Animal and let Cat be a subclass of Animal. So, any cat IS animal. Here, Cat satisfies the IS-A relationship for its own type as well as its super class Animal.

Note: It’s also legal to say every object in Java is polymorphic in nature, as each one passes an IS-A test for itself and also for Object class.

Static Polymorphism:

In Java, static polymorphism is achieved through method overloading. Method overloading means there are several methods present in a class having the same name but different types/order/number of parameters.

At compile time, Java knows which method to invoke by checking the method signatures. So, this is called **compile time polymorphism** or **static binding**. The concept will be clear from the following example:

```
class DemoOverload{
```

```

public int add(int x, int y){ //method 1
return x+y;
}
public int add(int x, int y, int z){ //method 2
return x+y+z;
}
public int add(double x, int y){ //method 3
return (int)x+y;
}
public int add(int x, double y){ //method 4
return x+(int)y;
}
}
class Test{
public static void main(String[] args){
    DemoOverload demo=new DemoOverload();
System.out.println(demo.add(2,3)); //method 1 called
System.out.println(demo.add(2,3,4)); //method 2 called
System.out.println(demo.add(2,3.4)); //method 4 called
System.out.println(demo.add(2.5,3)); //method 3 called
}
}

```

Output

5
9

5

5

Abstraction

Abstraction refers to the ability to make a class abstract in OOP. An abstract class is one that cannot be instantiated. All other functionality of the class still exists, and its fields, methods, and constructors are all accessed in the same manner. You just cannot create an instance of the abstract class.

If a class is abstract and cannot be instantiated, the class does not have much use unless it is subclass. This is typically how abstract classes come about during the design phase. A parent class contains the common functionality of a collection of child classes, but the parent class itself is too abstract to be used on its own.

Abstract Class:

Use the **abstract** keyword to declare a class abstract. The keyword appears in the class declaration somewhere before the class keyword.

```
/* File name : Employee.java */
public abstract class Employee
{
    private String name;
    private String address;
    private int number;
    public Employee(String name, String address, int number)
    {
        System.out.println("Constructing an Employee");
        this.name = name;
        this.address = address;
        this.number = number;
    }
    public double computePay()
    {
        System.out.println("Inside Employee computePay");
        return 0.0;
    }
    public void mailCheck()
    {
        System.out.println("Mailing a check to "+this.name+" "+this.address);
    }
    public String toString()
    {
        return name + " " + address + " " + number;
    }
    public String getName()
```

```

{
return name;
}
publicString getAddress()
{
return address;
}
publicvoid setAddress(String newAddress)
{
address= newAddress;
}
publicint getNumber()
{
return number;
}
}

```

Notice that nothing is different in this Employee class. The class is now abstract, but it still has three fields, seven methods, and one constructor.

Now if you would try as follows:

```

/* File name : AbstractDemo.java */
publicclassAbstractDemo
{
publicstaticvoid main(String[] args)
{
/* Following is not allowed and would raise error */
Employee e =newEmployee("George W.", "Houston, TX",43);

System.out.println("\n Call mailCheck using Employee reference--");
e.mailCheck();
}
}

```

When you would compile above class then you would get the following error:

```

Employee.java:46:Employeeisabstract; cannot be instantiated
Employee e =newEmployee("George W.", "Houston, TX",43);
^
1 error

```

Extending Abstract Class:

We can extend Employee class in normal way as follows:

```

/* File name : Salary.java */
publicclassSalaryextendsEmployee
{
privatedouble salary;//Annual salary
publicSalary(String name,String address,int number,double salary)
{
super(name, address, number);
setSalary(salary);
}
publicvoid mailCheck()
{
System.out.println("Within mailCheck of Salary class ");
System.out.println("Mailing check to "+ getName()
+" with salary "+ salary);
}
publicdouble getSalary()
{
return salary;
}
publicvoid setSalary(double newSalary)
{
if(newSalary >=0.0)
{
salary= newSalary;
}
}
publicdouble computePay()
{
System.out.println("Computing salary pay for "+ getName());
return salary/52;
}
}

```

Here, we cannot instantiate a new Employee, but if we instantiate a new Salary object, the Salary object will inherit the three fields and seven methods from Employee.

```

/* File name : AbstractDemo.java */
publicclassAbstractDemo
{
publicstaticvoid main(String[] args)
{
Salary s =newSalary("James Gosling","Indonesia",3,3600.00);
Employee e =newSalary("John Adams","Boston",2,2400.00);

System.out.println("Call mailCheck using Salary reference --");
s.mailCheck();
}
}

```

```
System.out.println("\n Call mailCheck using Employee reference--");
e.mailCheck();
}
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Constructing an Employee
Constructing an Employee
Call mailCheck usingSalary reference --
Within mailCheck of Salaryclass
Mailing check to James Goslingwith salary 3600.0

Call mailCheck usingEmployee reference--
Within mailCheck of Salaryclass
Mailing check to JohnAdamswith salary 2400.
```

Abstract Methods:

If you want a class to contain a particular method but you want the actual implementation of that method to be determined by child classes, you can declare the method in the parent class as abstract.

The abstract keyword is also used to declare a method as abstract. An abstract method consists of a method signature, but no method body.

Abstract method would have no definition, and its signature is followed by a semicolon, not curly braces as follows:

```
publicabstractclassEmployee
{
privateString name;
privateString address;
privateint number;

publicabstractdouble computePay();

//Remainder of class definition
}
```

Declaring a method as abstract has two results:

- The class must also be declared abstract. If a class contains an abstract method, the class must be abstract as well.

- Any child class must either override the abstract method or declare itself abstract.

A child class that inherits an abstract method must override it. If they do not, they must be abstract and any of their children must override it.

Abstract class in Java

A class that is declared with abstract keyword, is known as abstract class in java. It can have abstract and non-abstract methods (method with body).

Before learning java abstract class, let's understand the abstraction in java first

Abstraction in Java

Abstraction is a process of hiding the implementation details and showing only functionality to the user.

Another way, it shows only important things to the user and hides the internal details for example sending sms, you just type the text and send the message. You don't know the internal processing about the message delivery.

Abstraction lets you focus on what the object does instead of how it does it.

Ways to achieve Abstraction

There are two ways to achieve abstraction in java

1. Abstract class (0 to 100%)
2. Interface (100%)

Abstract class in Java

A class that is declared as abstract is known as **abstract class**. It needs to be extended and its method implemented. It cannot be instantiated.

Example abstract class

```
abstract class A{ }
```

abstract method

A method that is declared as abstract and does not have implementation is known as abstract method.

Example abstract method

```
abstract void printStatus();//no body and abstract
```

Example of abstract class that has abstract method

In this example, Bike the abstract class that contains only one abstract method run. Its implementation is provided by the Honda class.

1. **abstract class** Bike{
2. **abstract void** run();
3. }
4. **class** Honda4 **extends** Bike{
5. **void** run(){System.out.println("running safely..");}
6. **public static void** main(String args[]){
7. Bike obj = **new** Honda4();
8. obj.run();
9. }
10. }

Output
running safely..

Interfaces

An interface is a collection of abstract methods. A class implements an interface, thereby inheriting the abstract methods of the interface.

An interface is not a class. Writing an interface is similar to writing a class, but they are two different concepts. A class describes the attributes and behaviors of an object. An interface contains behaviors that a class implements.

Unless the class that implements the interface is abstract, all the methods of the interface need to be defined in the class.

An interface is similar to a class in the following ways:

- An interface can contain any number of methods.
- An interface is written in a file with a **.java** extension, with the name of the interface matching the name of the file.
- The bytecode of an interface appears in a **.class** file.
- Interfaces appear in packages, and their corresponding bytecode file must be in a directory structure that matches the package name.

However, an interface is different from a class in several ways, including:

- You cannot instantiate an interface.
- An interface does not contain any constructors.

- All of the methods in an interface are abstract.
- An interface cannot contain instance fields. The only fields that can appear in an interface must be declared both static and final.
- An interface is not extended by a class; it is implemented by a class.
- An interface can extend multiple interfaces.

Declaring Interfaces:

The **interface** keyword is used to declare an interface. Here is a simple example to declare an interface:

Example:

Let us look at an example that depicts encapsulation:

```

/* File name : NameOfInterface.java */
import java.lang.*;
//Any number of import statements

publicinterfaceNameOfInterface
{
//Any number of final, static fields
//Any number of abstract method declarations\
}

```

Interfaces have the following properties:

- An interface is implicitly abstract. You do not need to use the **abstract** keyword when declaring an interface.
- Each method in an interface is also implicitly abstract, so the abstract keyword is not needed.
- Methods in an interface are implicitly public.

Example:

```

/* File name : Animal.java */
interfaceAnimal{

publicvoid eat();
publicvoid travel();
}

```

Implementing Interfaces:

When a class implements an interface, you can think of the class as signing a contract, agreeing to perform the specific behaviors of the interface. If a class does not perform all the behaviors of the interface, the class must declare itself as abstract.

A class uses the **implements** keyword to implement an interface. The implements keyword appears in the class declaration following the extends portion of the declaration.

```
/* File name : MammalInt.java */
public class MammalInt implements Animal {

    public void eat() {
        System.out.println("Mammal eats");
    }

    public void travel() {
        System.out.println("Mammal travels");
    }

    public int noOfLegs() {
        return 0;
    }

    public static void main(String args[]) {
        MammalInt m = new MammalInt();
        m.eat();
        m.travel();
    }
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Mammal eats
Mammal travels
```

Java Interface Example

In this example, Printable interface has only one method, its implementation is provided in the A class.

```
1. interface printable{
2. void print();
3. }
4. class A6 implements printable{
5. public void print(){System.out.println("Hello");
6. }
7. public static void main(String args[]){
8. A6 obj = new A6();
9. obj.print();
10. }
11. }
    output
```

Hello

Exception Handling

Exception handling overview

An exception is a problem that arises during the execution of a program. An exception can occur for many different reasons, including the following:

- A user has entered invalid data.
- A file that needs to be opened cannot be found.
- A network connection has been lost in the middle of communications or the JVM has run out of memory.

Some of these exceptions are caused by user error, others by programmer error, and others by physical resources that have failed in some manner.

To understand how exception handling works in Java, you need to understand the **two categories** of exceptions:

- **Checked exceptions:** A checked exception is an exception that is typically a user error or a problem that cannot be foreseen by the programmer. For example, if a file is to be opened, but the file cannot be found, an exception occurs. These exceptions cannot simply be ignored at the time of compilation.
- **Unchecked exceptions**-includes **Runtime exceptions** and **Errors**
 - **Runtime exceptions:** A runtime exception is an exception that occurs that probably could have been avoided by the programmer. As opposed to checked exceptions, runtime exceptions are ignored at the time of compilation.
 - **Errors:** These are not exceptions at all, but problems that arise beyond the control of the user or the programmer. Errors are typically ignored in your code because you can rarely do anything about an error. For example, if a stack overflow occurs, an error will arise. They are also ignored at the time of compilation.

Exception Hierarchy

All exception classes are subtypes of the **java.lang.Exception class**. The exception class is a subclass of the **Throwable class**. Other than the exception class there is another subclass called **Error** which is derived from the Throwable class.

Errors are not normally trapped from the Java programs. These conditions normally happen in case of severe failures, which are not handled by the java programs. Errors are generated to indicate errors generated by the runtime environment. Example: JVM is out of Memory. Normally programs cannot recover from errors.

The Exception class has two main subclasses: IOException class and RuntimeException Class.

5	<p>public StackTraceElement [] getStackTrace()</p> <p>Returns an array containing each element on the stack trace. The element at index 0 represents the top of the call stack, and the last element in the array represents the method at the bottom of the call stack.</p>
6	<p>public Throwable fillInStackTrace()</p> <p>Fills the stack trace of this Throwable object with the current stack trace, adding to any previous information in the stack trace.</p>

Catching Exceptions

A method catches an exception using a combination of the **try** and **catch** keywords. A try/catch block is placed around the code that might generate an exception. Code within a try/catch block is referred to as protected code, and the syntax for using try/catch looks like the following:

```
try
{
//Protected code
} catch (ExceptionName e1)
{
//Catch block
}
```

A catch statement involves declaring the type of exception you are trying to catch. If an exception occurs in protected code, the catch block (or blocks) that follows the try is checked. If the type of exception that occurred is listed in a catch block, the exception is passed to the catch block much as an argument is passed into a method parameter.

Example:

The following is an array is declared with 2 elements. Then the code tries to access the 3rd element of the array which throws an exception.

```
// File Name : ExcepTest.java
```

```

import java.io.*;
public class ExcepTest {

    public static void main(String args[]) {
        try {
            int a[] = new int[2];
            System.out.println("Access element three : " + a[3]);
        } catch (ArrayIndexOutOfBoundsException e) {
            System.out.println("Exception thrown : " + e);
        }
        System.out.println("Out of the block");
    }
}

```

This would produce the following result:

```

Exception thrown : java.lang.ArrayIndexOutOfBoundsException:3
Out of the block

```

Multiple catch Blocks:

A try block can be followed by multiple catch blocks. The syntax for multiple catch blocks looks like the following:

```

try
{
    //Protected code
} catch (ExceptionType1 e1)
{
    //Catch block
} catch (ExceptionType2 e2)
{
    //Catch block
}

```

```
}catch(ExceptionType3 e3)
{
//Catch block
}
```

A method can declare that it throws more than one exception, in which case the exceptions are declared in a list separated by commas. For example, the following method declares that it throws a `RemoteException` and an `InsufficientFundsException`:

```
import java.io.*;
public class className
{
public void withdraw(double amount) throws RemoteException,
InsufficientFundsException
{
// Method implementation
}
//Remainder of class definition
}
```

The finally Keyword

The `finally` keyword is used to create a block of code that follows a `try` block. A `finally` block of code always executes, whether or not an exception has occurred.

Using a `finally` block allows you to run any cleanup-type statements that you want to execute, no matter what happens in the protected code.

A `finally` block appears at the end of the `catch` blocks and has the following syntax:

```
try
{
//Protected code
}catch(ExceptionType1 e1)
{
//Catch block
}catch(ExceptionType2 e2)
{
```

```
//Catch block
}catch(ExceptionType3 e3)
{
//Catch block
}finally
{
//The finally block always executes.
}
```

Example:

```
publicclassExcepTest{

publicstaticvoidmain(Stringargs[]){
inta[]=newint[2];
try{
System.out.println("Access element three :"+ a[3]);
}catch(ArrayIndexOutOfBoundsException e){
System.out.println("Exception thrown :"+ e);
}
finally{
a[0]=6;
System.out.println("First element value: "+a[0]);
System.out.println("The finally statement is executed");
}
}
}
```

This would produce the following result:

```
Exceptionthrown :java.lang.ArrayIndexOutOfBoundsException:3
First element value:6
Thefinally statement is executed
```

Note the following:

- A catch clause cannot exist without a try statement.
- It is not compulsory to have finally clauses whenever a try/catch block is present.
- The try block cannot be present without either catch clause or finally clause.

- Any code cannot be present in between the try, catch, finally blocks.

Declaring your own Exception

You can create your own exceptions in Java. Keep the following points in mind when writing your own exception classes:

- All exceptions must be a child of Throwable.
- If you want to write a checked exception that is automatically enforced by the Handle or Declare Rule, you need to extend the Exception class.
- If you want to write a runtime exception, you need to extend the RuntimeException class.

We can define our own Exception class as below:

```
classMyExceptionextendsException{  
}
```

Example:

```
// File Name InsufficientFundsException.java  
importjava.io.*;  
  
publicclassInsufficientFundsExceptionextendsException  
{  
    privatedouble amount;  
    publicInsufficientFundsException(double amount)  
    {  
        this.amount= amount;  
    }  
    publicdoublegetAmount()  
    {  
        return amount;  
    }  
}
```

```
}
```

To demonstrate using our user-defined exception, the following `CheckingAccount` class contains a `withdraw()` method that throws an `InsufficientFundsException`.

```
// File Name CheckingAccount.java
import java.io.*;

public class CheckingAccount
{
    private double balance;
    private int number;
    public CheckingAccount(int number)
    {
        this.number = number;
    }
    public void deposit(double amount)
    {
        balance += amount;
    }
    public void withdraw(double amount) throws
        InsufficientFundsException
    {
        if (amount <= balance)
        {
            balance -= amount;
        }
        else
        {
            double needs = amount - balance;
            throw new InsufficientFundsException(needs);
        }
    }
}
```

```

}
}
publicdoublegetBalance()
{
return balance;
}
publicintgetNumber()
{
return number;
}
}
}

```

The following BankDemo program demonstrates invoking the deposit() and withdraw() methods of CheckingAccount.

```

// File Name BankDemo.java
publicclassBankDemo
{
publicstaticvoidmain(String[]args)
{
CheckingAccount c =newCheckingAccount(101);
System.out.println("Depositing $500...");
c.deposit(500.00);
try
{
System.out.println("\nWithdrawing $100...");
c.withdraw(100.00);
System.out.println("\nWithdrawing $600...");
c.withdraw(600.00);
}catch(InsufficientFundsException e)
{

```

```
System.out.println("Sorry, but you are short $"
+e.getAmount());
e.printStackTrace();
}
}
}
```

Compile all the above three files and run BankDemo, this would produce the following result:

```
Depositing $500...

Withdrawing $100...

Withdrawing $600...
Sorry, but you are short $200.0
InsufficientFundsException
atCheckingAccount.withdraw(CheckingAccount.java:25)
atBankDemo.main(BankDemo.java:13)
```

Common Exceptions:

In Java, it is possible to define two categories of Exceptions and Errors.

- **JVM Exceptions:** - These are exceptions/errors that are exclusively or logically thrown by the JVM. Examples :NullPointerException, ArrayIndexOutOfBoundsException, ClassCastException,
- **Programmatic exceptions:** - These exceptions are thrown explicitly by the application or the API programmers Examples: IllegalArgumentException, IllegalStateException.

GUI and Java Applet

Overview of Applets

A Java applet is a special kind of Java application that is designed to work with a web browser. Java **Applets** are special in that they can only use a subset of the total functionality of the Java Virtual Machine. This is for several reasons:

- Java applets are usually compact, so that they can be easily downloaded across the web.
- Applets are not permitted to perform file or certain memory operations on the client machine, which prevents hostile applets from attacking a client machine, for example, trying to delete files on the machine or locking out resources.
- Applets have no main() method. Instead they have a set of methods that will be called in a particular order.

Packaged with the Java Software Development Kit (Java JDK 6) is an appletviewer. The **appletviewer** is the minimum requirement for a web-browser, that allows applets to run without having to use a full web browser. When calling the appletviewer you must pass the name of a HTML file that contains the <APPLET> tag, an extension to the HTML language. This <APPLET> tag specifies the name of the initial Java class to load and the initial width and height of the applet.

A Simple Applet Example - Hello World!

The easiest example to begin with is the Hello World example. There are two files that must be present in the same directory - example.html and HelloWorld.class. Once again - You need to have a web page in which to run an applet. The code in the HTML page called example.html should be something like:

```
1 <html>
2 <head>
3 <title> Test Applet Page </title></head>
4 <body>
5 <applet code=HelloWorld.class width=200 height=200>
6 </applet> ❶
7 </body>
8 </html>
```

- ❶ The <APPLET> tag is the only tag we are concerned with. The other tags are standard HTML.

The code in the Applet HelloWorld.java should look like:

```
1
2
3 // The HelloWorld Applet - Displays Hello World!
4 // at the pixel location (20,20)
5
6 import java.awt.Graphics;❶
7 import java.applet.Applet;
8
9 public class HelloWorld extends Applet❷
10 {
11     public void paint(Graphics g)❸
12     {
13         g.drawString("Hello World!",20,20);❹
14     }
15 }
16
17
```

- ❶ The packages (libraries) to include.
- ❷ Applet is the parent class.
- ❸ The paint() method is responsible for drawing to the screen.
- ❹ Draws the String object "Hello World!" to the (20,20) screen location.

The Life Cycle of an Applet

The life cycle of the applet has the following stages:

- The appletviewer loads and creates the specified class.
- The applet initializes itself.
- The applet starts running.
- When finished the applet is destroyed.

The applet always receives an init() method first and then a start() and paint() call (Note: This may happen asynchronously! i.e. at the same time).

To use the `java.applet.Applet` class to make a useful applet you must create a subclass of Applet. To do this, you must override some (or all) of the following methods:

- ❖ `init()` - This method 'sets-up' the applet, called once when the applet is first initialized. Use this method to set up the display of the applet, set colours etc.
- ❖ `start()` - Called whenever the applet is visited, i.e. the applet starts running again. You could use this method to start up an animation that stops when the applet is minimised. This method would be called when the web browser has been restored after being minimised.
- ❖ `stop()` - Called when the applet is no longer active (e.g. minimized)
- ❖ `paint()` - This method is called whenever the appearance of the applet is required to be updated, such as when the applet is being maximized from a minimized state. The appearance needs to be updated. It is also possible for the programmer to call this method. This method does nothing by default, you must write the code.
- ❖ `destroy()` - Called when the applet is discarded. This method should perform any closing down tasks that you would wish to perform, such as closing connections to databases, etc.

This Applet now looks like this: The source code for **HelloWorld2.java** is:

```

1
2
3 // The HelloWorld2 Applet - Allows the modification of the parameters
4 // that are displayed in the applet.
5
6 import java.awt.Graphics;
7 import java.applet.Applet;
8
9 public class HelloWorld2 extends Applet
10 {
11 // The class states - declared here so that the parameters can be passed
12 // from the init() method to the paint() method. These states are given
  
```

```

13 // default values of World to be displayed at (10,10)
14
15 private String theDisplayString = "World";
16 private int theStartx = 10;
17 private int theStarty = 10;
18
19 public void init()
20 {
21 // try to read in the parameters from the HTML file
22     String tempName = this.getParameter("displayName");
23     String tempXString = this.getParameter("startx");
24     String tempYString = this.getParameter("starty");
25
26 // check to see if any of the parameters are blank
27
28 if ((tempName!=null)&&(tempXString!=null)&&(tempYString!=null))
29 {
30 // OK - none of the parameters are blank
31 // the HTML author did their job properly
32
33 this.theDisplayString = tempName;
34
35 // convert the (X,Y) strings received into integer values.
36 this.theStartx = (new Integer(tempXString)).intValue();
37 this.theStarty = (new Integer(tempYString)).intValue();
38 }
39 }
40
41 public void paint(Graphics g)
42 {
43 g.drawString("Hello "+theDisplayString+"!",theStartx,theStarty);
44 }
45 }
46
47

```

This code will result in an applet that looks like

Displaying Graphics in Applets

Java provides a straightforward (but advanced) mechanism for loading images. Just to put the difficulties in context with loading images in applets; As you are aware, applets are downloaded from an Internet site, which implies that if we are to use images in our applets, they must also be downloaded from an Internet site as separate files. So the image loader must be 'Internet aware', but that's only the start; what if we have a very slow connection between your computer (onto which the applet downloads) and the site with the image. Our applet needs to download the image, before it runs, or does it? - well no in fact, as a threaded application it can continue doing other tasks while it is waiting for the image to download completely.

Applets have built in support for images, including the ability to decode and display GIF (.gif) and JPEG (.jpg) image format files. Image files are assumed to be relative to where the applet was loaded from, i.e. the base directory. A good way to determine the **base directory** that the applet is located by using the `getDocumentBase()` method of the `Appletclass`, that returns the base directory as a URL (uniform resource locator) object. You can then pass this URL object to a special Applet method for loading an image. It requires a URL and an optional filename of the image to load. For Example:

```
Image myImage = this.getImage (this.getDocumentBase(),"theImage.gif");
```

This method call will create an `Image` object called `myImage` and in effect place the loaded image in this image object. This operation actually creates a separate thread, allowing the `paint()` method of the applet could be called, even though the entire image may not have been loaded. The image will not be drawn until it is completely loaded.

To draw this image to the screen use the `drawImage()` method of the `Graphics` class. You would usually place this call in the `paint()` method of your applet. The syntax of this call is:

(within the java.awt.Graphics class)

```
boolean drawImage(Image img, int x, int y, ImageObserver observer)
```

Where `img` is your image object, `x` and `y` represent the position to draw the top-left corner of the image. The observer is the object to be notified as more of the image is decoded. The `drawImage` returns a false value if the image has not yet been completely loaded and then returns true when the image has finally loaded.

So an example use of `drawImage()` might be:

```
g.drawImage(myImage, 20, 20, this);
```

allowing us to draw the image object that we loaded above to the (x,y) position (20,20) and sets the image observer as this. The Java keyword `this` refers to "this object of the current Class" - so in our case it would refer to "this instance of our Applet class". So our applet is concerned with notification of the image loading.

Here is an example of using the methods just discussed to display an image twice in an applet. This applet assumes that the image file "test.gif" is in the same directory as the applet class file "ImageApplet.class".


```
// The ImageApplet that displays an example image "test.gif"
```

```
import java.awt.Graphics;
```

```

import java.awt.Image;
import java.applet.Applet;

public class ImageApplet extends Applet
{
private Image theImage;

public void init()
{
    this.theImage = this.getImage( this.getDocumentBase(), "test.gif" );
}

public void paint(Graphics g)
{
    g.drawImage( this.theImage, 10, 10, this);
    g.drawImage( this.theImage, 100, 100, this);
}
}

```

In this code segment theImage object has been made a state of the class to allow it to be accessed from both the init() and the paint() methods of our applet ImageApplet. Note that we have not called a constructor for theImage object as the getImage() method actually returns a constructed Image object.

Playing Audio Clips

As well as support for displaying images, applets also have support for playing sound (provided that the client machine has hardware support for playing audio clips). The easiest way to play sounds in applets is by using the play() method. This is very useful for playing simple sounds, especially when starting and stopping applets. The method has the syntax:

```

// In java.applet.Applet
void play(URL url, String name)

```

where the first argument is the base directory of the applet and the second argument is the sound file to play. It can be used like:

```

this.play( this.getDocumentBase(), "theSound.au");

```

The `play()` method requires that the applet `.class` file and the sound clip are below the same directory. For a more complicated use of sounds you could use:

```
// In java.applet.Applet
AudioClip getAudioClip(URL url, String name)
```

where this method returns an object of the `java.applet.AudioClip` Interface (no not a class, we will discuss this again). We can then use the `play()`, `loop()` or `stop()` methods of this object. Multiple `AudioClip` objects can be playing at the same time, and the resulting sound is mixed together to produce a composite.

Task: Write an Java applet that plays a sound when it is minimized and a different sound when it is once again maximised

Solution: Ok there is no point this time to show a picture as it just plays audio, but here `SoundApplet.html` is my solution applet. The source code is below and `atSoundApplet.java`

```
// The SoundApplet that plays a different sound on start and stop

import java.applet.Applet;
import java.applet.AudioClip;

public class SoundApplet extends Applet
{
    private AudioClip theStartSound, theStopSound;

    public void init()
    {
        this.theStartSound = this.getAudioClip( this.getDocumentBase(), "start.wav" );
        this.theStopSound = this.getAudioClip( this.getDocumentBase(), "stop.wav" );
    }

    public void start()
    {
        this.theStartSound.play();
    }
}
```

```
public void stop()
{
this.theStopSound.play();
}
}
```

Executing an applet

Follow the following steps to execute an applet:

- Create
 - Applet file
 - Save as **AppletName.java** (Where **AppletName**-is file name of the applet)
- Compile
 - The applet as **javac AppletName.java**
 - If no errors, bytecodes will be generated with **AppletName.class**
- Create an HTML file
 - Link **AppletName.class** to the HTML file using the **<applet>** tag
 - Save the HTML file with extension **.htm** or **.html** **in the same directory with the applet file**
- To run an applet
 - Open the HTML file saved earlier if you have java-enabled browser or
 - Type **appletviewer HTML-FileName.html** on command prompt to useJVM's applet viewer

Java Applets Vs Java Application

There are some important differences between an applet and a standalone Java application, including the following:

- ❖ An applet is a Java class that extends the `java.applet.Applet` class.
- ❖ A `main()` method is not invoked on an applet, and an applet class will not define `main()`.
- ❖ Applets are designed to be embedded within an HTML page.
- ❖ When a user views an HTML page that contains an applet, the code for the applet is downloaded to the user's machine.
- ❖ A JVM is required to view an applet. The JVM can be either a plug-in of the Web browser or a separate runtime environment.
- ❖ The JVM on the user's machine creates an instance of the applet class and invokes various methods during the applet's lifetime.

- ❖ Applets have strict security rules that are enforced by the Web browser. The security of an applet is often referred to as sandbox security, comparing the applet to a child playing in a sandbox with various rules that must be followed.

Application

- ✓ Trusted (i.e., has full access to system resources)
- ✓ Invoked by Java Virtual Machine (JVM, java), e.g., java HelloWorld
- ✓ Should contain a main method, i.e., public static void main(String[])

Applet

- ✓ Not trusted (i.e., has limited access to system resource to prevent security breaches)
- ✓ Invoked automatically by the web browser
- ✓ Should be a subclass of class java.applet.Applet

Java Swing

Java Swing tutorial is a part of Java Foundation Classes (JFC) that is *used to create window-based applications*. It is built on the top of AWT (Abstract Windowing Toolkit) API and entirely written in java.

Unlike AWT, Java Swing provides platform-independent and lightweight components.

The javax.swing package provides classes for java swing API such as JButton, JTextField, JTextArea, JRadioButton, JCheckBox, JMenu, JColorChooser etc.

Difference between AWT and Swing

There are many differences between java awt and swing that are given below.

No.	Java AWT	Java Swing
1)	AWT components are platform-dependent .	Java swing components are platform-independent .
2)	AWT components are heavyweight .	Swing components are lightweight .
3)	AWT doesn't support pluggable look and feel .	Swing supports pluggable look and feel .
4)	AWT provides less components than Swing.	Swing provides more powerful components such as tables, lists, scrollpanes, colorchooser, tabbedpane etc.

5)	AWT doesn't follows MVC (Model View Controller) where model represents data, view represents presentation and controller acts as an interface between model and view.	Swing follows MVC .
----	--	----------------------------

Java Swing Examples

There are two ways to create a frame:

- By creating the object of Frame class (association)
- By extending Frame class (inheritance)

We can write the code of swing inside the main(), constructor or any other method.

Simple Java Swing Example

Let's see a simple swing example where we are creating one button and adding it on the JFrame object inside the main() method.

File: FirstSwingExample.java

1. **import** javax.swing.*;
2. **public class** FirstSwingExample {
3. **public static void** main(String[] args) {
4. JFrame f=**new** JFrame();//creating instance of JFrame
5. JButton b=**new** JButton("click");//creating instance of JButton
6. b.setBounds(130,100,100, 40);//x axis, y axis, width, height
7. f.add(b);//adding button in JFrame
8. f.setSize(400,500);//400 width and 500 height
9. f.setLayout(**null**);//using no layout managers
10. f.setVisible(**true**);//making the frame visible

Java AWT

Java AWT (Abstract Window Toolkit) is *an API to develop GUI or window-based applications* in java.

Java AWT components are platform-dependent i.e. components are displayed according to the view of operating system. AWT is heavyweight i.e. its components are using the resources of OS.

The java.awt package provides classes for AWT api such as TextField, Label, TextArea, RadioButton, CheckBox, Choice, List etc.

Java AWT Hierarchy

The hierarchy of Java AWT classes are given below.

Java AWT Example

To create simple awt example, you need a frame. There are two ways to create a frame in AWT.

- By extending Frame class (inheritance)
- By creating the object of Frame class (association)

AWT Example by Inheritance

Let's see a simple example of AWT where we are inheriting Frame class. Here, we are showing Button component on the Frame.

1. **import** java.awt.*;

```

2. class First extends Frame{
3. First(){
4. Button b=new Button("click me");
5. b.setBounds(30,100,80,30);// setting button position
6. add(b);//adding button into frame
7. setSize(300,300);//frame size 300 width and 300 height
8. setLayout(null);//no layout manager
9. setVisible(true);//now frame will be visible, by default not visible
10. }
11. public static void main(String args[]){
12. First f=new First();
13. }}

```

The `setBounds(int xaxis, int yaxis, int width, int height)` method is used in the above example that sets the position of the awt button.

Event Handling

Any program that uses GUI (graphical user interface) such as Java application written for windows, is event driven. Event describes the change of state of any object. **Example :** Pressing a button, Entering a character in Textbox.

Components of Event Handling

Event handling has three main components,

- **Events :** An event is a change of state of an object.
- **Events Source :** Event source is an object that generates an event.
- **Listeners :** A listener is an object that listens to the event. A listener gets notified when an event occurs.

How Events are handled ?

A source generates an Event and send it to one or more listeners registered with the source. Once event is received by the listener, they processe the event and then return. Events are supported by a number of Java packages, like **java.util**, **java.awt** and **java.awt.event**.

Important Event Classe and Interface

Event Classe	Description
ActionEvent	generated when button is pressed, menu-item is selected, list-item is double clicked
MouseEvent	generated when mouse is dragged, moved,clicked,pressed or released also when the enters or exit a component
KeyEvent	generated when input is received from keyboard
ItemEvent	generated when check-box or list item is clicked
TextEvent	generated when value of textarea or textfield is changed
MouseEvent	generated when mouse wheel is moved
WindowEvent	generated when window is activated, deactivated, deiconified, iconified, opened or closed
ComponentEvent	generated when component is hidden, moved, resized or set visible
ContainerEvent	generated when component is added or removed from container
AdjustmentEvent	generated when scroll bar is manipulated
FocusEvent	generated when component gains or loses keyboard focus

Example of Event Handling

```
import java.awt.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.applet.*;
import java.applet.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.awt.*;

public class Test extends Applet implements KeyListener
{
    String msg="";
    public void init()
    {
        addKeyListener(this);
    }
    public void keyPressed(KeyEvent k)
    {
        showStatus("KeyPressed");
    }
    public void keyReleased(KeyEvent k)
    {
        showStatus("KeyRealesed");
    }
    public void keyTyped(KeyEvent k)
    {
        msg = msg+k.getKeyChar();
        repaint();
    }
    public void paint(Graphics g)
    {
        g.drawString(msg, 20, 40);
    }
}
```

```
}
```

HTML code :

```
<applet code="Test" width=300, height=100 >
```


AWT

AWT contains large number of classes and methods that allows you to create and manage windows GUI application. AWT is the foundation upon which **Swing** is made. It is used for GUI programming in Java. But now a days it is merely used because most GUI java programs are implemented using **Swing** because of its rich implementation of GUI controls and light-weighted nature.

AWT Hierarchy

Component class

Component class is at the top of AWT hierarchy. Component is an abstract class that encapsulates all attribute of visual component. A component object is responsible for remembering the current foreground and background colours and the currently selected text font.

Container

Container is a component in AWT that contains another component like button, text field, tables etc. **Container** is a subclass of component class. **Container** class keeps track of components that are added to another component.

Panel

Panel class is concrete sub class of **Container**. Panel does not contain title bar, menu bar or border.

Window class

Window class creates a top level window. Window does not have borders and menubar.

Frame

Frame is a sub class of **Window** and have resizing canvas. It is a container that contain several different components like button, title bar, textfield, label etc. In Java, most of the AWT applications are created using **Frame** window. Frame class has two different constructors,

Frame() throws **HeadlessException**

Frame(String title) throws **HeadlessException**

Creating a Frame

There are two ways to create a Frame. They are,

1. By Instantiating Frame class
2. By extending Frame class

Creating Frame Window by Instantiating Frame class

```
import java.awt.*;

public class Testawt
{
    Testawt()
    {
        Frame fm=new Frame();    //Creating a frame.

        Label lb = new Label("welcome to java graphics");    //Creating a label

        fm.add(lb);                //adding label to the frame.

        fm.setSize(300, 300);    //setting frame size.

        fm.setVisible(true);    //set frame visibilty true.

    }

    public static void main(String args[])
    {

        Testawt ta = new Testawt();
```

```
}  
}
```


Creating Frame window by extending Frame class

```
package testawt;  
  
import java.awt.*;  
import java.awt.event.*;  
  
public class Testawt extends Frame  
{  
    public Testawt()  
    {  
        Button btn=new Button("Hello World");  
        add(btn);           //adding a new Button.  
        setSize(400, 500); //setting size.  
        setTitle("scanfree"); //setting title.  
    }  
}
```

```
setLayout(new FlowLayout());    //set default layout for frame.  
setVisible(true);    //set frame visibilty true.  
  
}  
public static void main (String[] args)  
{  
    Testawt ta = new Testawt(); //creating a frame.  
}  
}
```


Swing

Swing Framework contains a set of classes that provides more powerful and flexible GUI components than those of **AWT**. **Swing** provides the look and feel of modern Java GUI. Swing library is an official Java GUI tool kit released by Sun Microsystems. It is used to create graphical user interface with Java.

Main Features of Swing Toolkit

1. Platform Independent
2. Customizable
3. Extensible
4. Configurable
5. Lightweight

Swing and JFC

JFC is an abbreviation for Java Foundation classes, which encompass a group of features for building Graphical User Interfaces(GUI) and adding rich graphical functionalities and interactivity to Java applications.

Swing Component

Swing Framework contains a large set of components which provide rich functionalities and allow high level of customization. All these components are lightweight components. They all are derived from **JComponent** class. It supports the pluggable look and feel.

JButton

JButton class provides functionality of a button. **JButton** class has three constructors,

JButton(Icon *ic*)

JButton(String *str*)

JButton(String *str*, Icon *ic*)

It allows a button to be created using icon, a string or both. **JButton** supports **ActionEvent**. When a button is pressed an **ActionEvent** is generated.

Example using **JButton**

```

import javax.swing.*;

import java.awt.event.*;

import java.awt.*;

public class testswing extends JFrame
{

testswing()
{
    JButton bt1 = new JButton("Yes");           //Creating a Yes Button.
    JButton bt2 = new JButton("No");           //Creating a No Button.
    setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE) //setting close operation.
    setLayout(new FlowLayout());               //setting layout using FlowLayout object
    setSize(400, 400);                         //setting size of JFrame
    add(bt1);                                   //adding Yes button to frame.
    add(bt2);                                   //adding No button to frame.

    setVisible(true);
}

public static void main(String[] args)
{
    new testswing();
}
}

```


JTextField

JTextField is used for taking input of single line of text. It is most widely used text component. It has three constructors,

JTextField(int *cols*)

JTextField(String *str*, int *cols*)

JTextField(String *str*)

cols represent the number of columns in text field.

Example using JTextField

```
import javax.swing.*;
```

```
import java.awt.event.*;
```

```
import java.awt.*;
```

```
public class MyTextField extends JFrame
```

```
{
```

```
public MyTextField()
{
    JTextField jtf = new JTextField(20);    //creating JTextField.
    add(jtf);                               //adding JTextField to frame.
    setLayout(new FlowLayout());
    setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);
    setSize(400, 400);
    setVisible(true);
}

public static void main(String[] args)
{
    new MyTextField();
}
}
```


JCheckBox

JCheckBox class is used to create checkboxes in frame. Following is constructor for JCheckBox,

JCheckBox(String *str*)

Example using JCheckBox

```
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.awt.*;

public class Test extends JFrame
{
    public Test()
    {
```

```
JCheckBox jcb = new JCheckBox("yes"); //creating JCheckBox.  
add(jcb); //adding JCheckBox to frame.  
jcb = new JCheckBox("no"); //creating JCheckBox.  
add(jcb); //adding JCheckBox to frame.  
jcb = new JCheckBox("maybe"); //creating JCheckBox.  
add(jcb); //adding JCheckBox to frame.  
  
setLayout(new FlowLayout());  
setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);  
setSize(400, 400);  
setVisible(true);  
}  
  
public static void main(String[] args)  
{  
    new Test();  
}
```


JRadioButton

Radio button is a group of related button in which only one can be selected. JRadioButton class is used to create a radio button in Frames. Following is the constructor for JRadioButton,

JRadioButton(String str)

Example using JRadioButton

```
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.awt.*;

public class Test extends JFrame
{
    public Test()
    {
        JRadioButton jcb = new JRadioButton("A");    //creating JRadioButton.
        add(jcb);                                     //adding JRadioButton to frame.
        jcb = new JRadioButton("B");                //creating JRadioButton.
        add(jcb);                                     //adding JRadioButton to frame.
        jcb = new JRadioButton("C");                //creating JRadioButton.
        add(jcb);                                     //adding JRadioButton to frame.
        jcb = new JRadioButton("none");
        add(jcb);
        setLayout(new FlowLayout());
        setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);
        setSize(400, 400);
        setVisible(true);
    }

    public static void main(String[] args)
```

```

{
new Test();
}
}

```


JComboBox

Combo box is a combination of text fields and drop-down list. **JComboBox** component is used to create a combo box in Swing. Following is the constructor for JComboBox,

```
JComboBox(String arr[])
```

Example using JComboBox

```

import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.awt.*;

public class Test extends JFrame
{
    String name[] = {"Abhi","Adam","Alex","Ashkay"}; //list of name.
    public Test()
    {

```

```
JComboBox jc = new JComboBox(name);//initialzing combo box with list of name.  
add(jc); //adding JComboBox to frame.  
setLayout(new FlowLayout());  
setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);  
setSize(400, 400);  
setVisible(true);  
}  
public static void main(String[] args)  
{  
new Test();  
}  
}
```

